

Marketing Your Mobile App, The Steps For Continued Success

#android #ios #webdev #marketing

Krowser Web Services 30 May • 2 min read

Here are some tips for continued success in marketing your app to new users and maintaining your existing userbase.

Ask Users For Feedback

If people are using your app constantly, it is a sign that have made a connection with the product. Give them the opportunity to express their opinions with a popup invitation to leave a review, but remember that user experience should not be sacrificed by this tactic. Think about when and how you want to ask for a review and make sure it flows well with the user experience so it won't frustrate users. The more strategically the popup is placed, the better the chances are for a positive review.

Consider A Burst Campaign

A "burst campaign" is one of the most popular techniques used by mobile app marketers who want to climb the app store ranks. The idea of a burst campaign is to provide a "burst" of exposure for your app in which you aggressively purchase paid media exposure over a short period of time – usually between 24 and 72 hours, depending on budget. The goal is to get as many paid installs as possible, boosting your ranking. All this with the hope of increasing the volume of quality organic installs – that should follow when the app is finally ranked high enough to be discovered. While you should attract more organic downloads from a successful burst campaign, continued paid advertising will maintain steady downloads. You need to keep the momentum going.

Offer A Referral Bonus

Offering your users a bonus or benefit when they promote your app online is a surefire way to get them to spread the word. With a staggering 3900% growth rate, Dropbox is an excellent example of how powerful referrals can be. The company had just 1,00,000 registered users in 2008, which climbed to a staggering 4,000,000 registered users within a mere 15 month period as a result of their referral program. This post from Localvtics

... explains how Dropbox used referrals to exponentially increase their user base

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